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YELLOW FEVER VULNERABILITY AND RISK PATTERN: A GEOSPATIAL ANALYSIS OF THE 2019 AND 2020 CASES IN BAUCHI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Bauchi has recently experienced yellow fever outbreak, it is therefore critical to look at the spatio-temporal pattern, vulnerability and risk factors for the disease. This was accomplished by first building a database of illness cases based on their location, and then utilizing IDW interpolation ArcGIS 10.3 software to create disease maps for the outbreak. Optimised hotspot analysis was used to identify the concentration of yellow fever cases in the local government areas within the study area, and spatial auto-correlation was utilized to determine the pattern of yellow fever spread. The factors aiding yellow fever spread (euclidean distance for monkeys, mosquitoes, and forest along with temperature, rainfall, altitude, and built-up) were assessed for vulnerability. To identify places sensitive to yellow fever within the research area, a multicriteria analysis was conducted using weighted sum overlay to integrate the yellow fever risk factors. Both the 2019 and 2020 outbreaks have a random pattern of spread, with Moran's Index values of -0.070041 and 0.074746, respectively. In 2019, the Alkaleri local government area was identified as a hotspot for yellow fever outbreaks, followed by Ganjuwa in 2020. The entire research area is at risk of yellow fever spread, according to the Multicriteria analysis. Bauchi State is threatened by the spread of yellow fever outbreaks with more widespread in the southern part of the state. Because there is no known active antiviral treatment, the study suggests immunization and mitigating measures such as vector control as the options.*

Keywords: Cluster, Hotspot, Multicriteria, Risk, Vulnerability

INTRODUCTION

Front-line public health organizations play an important role in detecting and reacting to infectious disease outbreaks. Yellow fever, a neglected vector-borne disease is one of infectious diseases that has resurfaced. Yellow fever virus (YFV), is transmitted by *Aedes aegypti* mosquito bites in Africa and

Haemegogus and *Sabethes* mosquito bites in South America. It is an endemic viral vector-borne illness of Sub-Saharan Africa and South America (Chippaux & Chippaux, 2018; Sheff, 2018). The yellow fever virus is endemic in primate groups in Sub-Saharan Africa and South America, with periodic epidemics in the nations surrounding those regions (Barnett, 2007). There are forty-four countries in the

endemic area, with a combined population of approximately one billion people. With Africa accounting for 90% of infection, it was estimated that 120,000 cases and 45,000 fatalities occurred in Africa alone in 2013. (WHO, 2019).

The first outbreak of the disease in Nigeria was reported in Lagos in 1864, and subsequent outbreaks were reported on a regular basis until 1996 (Adogo and Ogoh, 2020). No further verified cases of Yellow fever were reported for another 21 years until September 2017, and since then, Nigeria has been witnessing occasional outbreaks of the disease (Adogo & Ogoh, 2020). In 2019, a possible case of yellow fever was discovered in Kano State, with a travel history to Yankari game reserve in Alkaleri Local Government Area (Bauchi State), Nigeria. According to the Nigerian Center for Disease Control NCDC (Put the year here), 231 suspected cases have been reported in four states of Bauchi (110), Borno (109), Gombe (10) and Kano (2), with 13 presumptive positive cases and 24 cases positive by reverse-transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) at national laboratories. Six deaths were recorded, all from Alkaleri in Bauchi state, of the 24 cases confirmed by RT-PCR; 20 of the cases were recorded in Bauchi, three in Gombe, and one in Kano state). This results in a case fatality ratio of 25% among the confirmed cases. Since the outbreak began in Nigeria in

September 2017, however, comparable instances have been documented in this area. In November 2019, 29 people were declared deceased in Bauchi state (out of 110 cases), with 24 in Alkaleri local government, two in Bauchi local government, one in Darazo council area, and two in Ningi local government (WHO, 2019).

In various parts of the world, several research on yellow fever have been undertaken utilizing diverse methods of analysis and reporting trend and distribution of YF. Some of those studies include Arden (2005); ; Rogers *et al.*, (2006); Jentes *et al.*, (2011); Garske *et al.*, (2014); Monath and Vasconcelos (2015); Chen and Lu (2016); Lüge (2017); Shearer *et al.*, (2018); Ihinegbu *et al.*, (2021); Amaku, Coutinho and Massad (2021) among others. However, despite the advances in GIS expertise and the recurrence of yellow fever outbreaks, very few studies have used the technology to map the spatial pattern of yellow fever outbreaks in Nigeria's Bauchi state.

THE STUDY AREA

Bauchi State, the study area in this investigation is located between latitudes 9° 3' and 12° 3' N and longitudes 8° 50' and 11° 00' E. It is bordered on the northwest by Jigawa and Kano, on the west by Kaduna, on the south by Plateau, Taraba, and Gombe, and on the east by Yobe (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Bauchi State with Nigeria as Inset

Source: GIS Lab. BUK

Rainfall in Bauchi state, ranges from 700 mm per year in the far north to 1,300 mm per year in the south. Rainfall in the West African sub-region mainly come from the south, transported by the south westerlies (Sylvester & Abdulquadir, 2015). As a result, there is a gradual dryness in the north, culminating in desert conditions in the extreme north. Rainy season usually begins sooner in the southern section of the state, where it is the heaviest and lasts for a longer period of time. Similarly, relative humidity varies greatly between the south and the north, with the south experiencing humidly hot weather during the early part of the rainy season, while the north has hot, dry, and dusty weather (Eludoyin *et al.*, 2014). Rainfall has made vegetables and water available in many regions, allowing mosquitoes to thrive, especially the YF-transmitting *Aedes aegypti*.

In 2006, the state had a population of 4,676,465 people living on a land area of 17,698 square miles (45,837 square kilometers). The Jos

Plateau is an extension of the highlands in the state's south western corner. The Gongola River rises in the Jos Plateau and runs northeast before turning south (roughly along the state's eastern border) and merging into the Benue River in Adamawa state. A vast number of ethnic groups live in Bauchi state, including the Tangale, Waja (Wajawa), Fulani, and Hausa (Sylvester & Abdulquadir, 2015). Bauchi state is one of the northern Nigerian states that straddles two separate vegetation zones, the Sudan savannah and the Sahel savannah (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2009). The Sudan savannah type of vegetation covers the southern part of the state, where the vegetation becomes increasingly richer as one travels south, especially along water sources or rivers, but the vegetation is less uniform and grasses are shorter than what grows even further south, in the middle belt's forest zone (Eludoyin *et al.*, 2014).

As one proceeds from the state's south to its north, the Sahel type of savannah, sometimes known as semi-desert flora, becomes more visible. Isolated stands of prickly shrubs make up this type of vegetation. The continuance of the Jos Plateau, on the other hand, has made the state mountainous in the south west, while the northern section is mostly sandy (Eludoyin *et al.*, 2014). The environment, particularly in the Yankari Game Reserve, is home to a large number of monkeys, making it ideal for YFV to grow.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Records of yellow fever cases used in the study were downloaded from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control website.. Landsat 8 images (30 x 30m resolution) from September 2019 to December 2020 were obtained from USGS earth explorer and utilized for landuse classification. This research period's climate data for Bauchi state was downloaded from <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer>. Bauchi state, local government, and administrative border shape files are examples of other types of data. ArcGIS 10.3 software, a laptop, Microsoft Excel, and ENVI 5.3 are some of the resources and program used during the study.

Bauchi State boundary shape files and that of the areas and/or local government areas with cases of yellow fever were extracted along with the records of YF cases which was then imported into ArcGIS 10.3 environment. Join and relate operations were performed and then interpolated using the spatial analyst tool based on Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW). A linear series graph was generated using excel Microsoft office package 2016 with the examples from 2019 and 2020 to determine the extent of the yellow spread. Cluster Analysis was used to determine the distribution pattern. The global Moran's index was calculated using

the spatial analyst tool in ArcGIS 10.3, which assesses spatial auto-correlation that falls between 1 and +1. Greater spatial clustering or competitive dispersion corresponds to more positive or negative values, respectively. Local Indicators of Spatial Auto-correlation (LISA) maps were constructed using local Moran's index computations to depict spatial grouping. In comparison to neighboring regions, this statistic highlights noteworthy sites as high-high or low-low spatial clusters, as well as high-low or low-high geographical outliers. In both indexes, regions with fewer neighbors are not included in the analysis.

Optimized hotspots analysis from the spatial statistic tool in the ArcToolbox of ArcGIS 10.3 was used to find the region within the study area with the highest number of cases of yellow fever. The Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic, which uses a default count incident point within fishnet polygons was used as the incident data aggregation method, this analysis provides a map of statistically significant hotspots (areas with high yellow fever cases) and coldspots (areas with low yellow fever cases). The software creates polygons from the points and then aggregates them into the polygons. The fishnet polygon technique generates a map of yellow fever event cases with comparable attribute values and classifies them as coldspots (blue areas) or hotspots (red areas) automatically. To combine the spatial and non-spatial data of the study area, the satellite imageries were initially mosaicked. Using ENVI 5.3 software, the image was classified based on land characteristics into forest, waterbody, built up and agricultural land.

After determining the primary elements that increase the occurrence of yellow fever in humans, a spatial multi-criteria analysis was used to determine the area vulnerable to yellow fever outbreak in the research area. Human activities (land use and cover), mosquitoes, and

animal hosts were all regarded as risk factors for yellow fever, with the climate and ecological environment all playing a role. An international expert group from the World Health Organization (WHO) chose the pertinent parameters and variables which were used in the Analytical Hierarchical Process, which assigns a scale of importance between the factors identified as given in Table 1, was used to weight each factor or theme layer.

The land use and land cover classification analysis resulted in the creation of forest and built-up shapefiles. The Euclidean distance was used to determine how far mosquitoes can travel; this is because built-up areas within 11 kilometers of their breeding zones, such as forests and waterbodies are vulnerable to the spread of yellow fever.

Table 1: Factors Associated with Vulnerability Criteria and their Weights

S/No	Factors	Assigned Weight (%)
1	Forest Distance	29.86
2	Monkey	29.86
3	Built-up	13.10
4	Temperature	5.63
5	Mosquito	13.10
6	Rainfall	2.83
7	Altitude	5.63

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The influence of monkey as a carrier of yellow fever virus on yellow fever propagation was also investigated using Euclidean distance. The spatial analyst tool in ArcGIS 10.3 was then used to interpolate temperature, rainfall, and altitude using inverse distance weighted (IDW). Using the Conversion tool and the spatial analyst tool in ArcMap's ArcTool box, each of the factors was converted to raster and reclassified (Figure 2).

The yellow fever risk indicators were combined using the weighed sum overlay and a yellow fever vulnerability of the research region was obtained. The vulnerability map was overlaid with shape files for 2019 and 2020 yellow fever cases in the study area.

Figure 2: Yellow Fever Risk Factors

Source: Field Survey (2022)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DISTRIBUTION PATTERN OF YELLOW FEVER

2019 and From January to December 2020, organized by the local government area of occurrence.

Figure 3 depicts yellow fever cases in Bauchi state from September to December

Figure 3:

Trend of Yellow Fever Cases in Bauchi State (2019-2020)

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The outbreak began in the Yankari game reserve in the Alkaleri local government region of Bauchi state in 2019 and spread to other villages and local government areas. The outbreak in Bauchi state in 2019 resulted in 115 cases dispersed in six local government areas: Alkaleri (84), Bauchi (7), Dass (4), Ganjuwa (10), Tafawa Balewa (9) and Toro (9) (1). In the first half of 2020 (January to December), the outbreak spread to three new local government areas in Bauchi: Jama'are (6), Ningi (2), and Warji (1). Between January and December 2020, 153 instances were reported, with Ganjuwa reporting the most (142), Bauchi Local Government Area reporting one new case, and Tafawa Balewa reporting one new

case apiece. Cases of yellow fever epidemic in the study area were cartographically rendered as polygons with respect to patients' location using inverse distance weighted (IDW) interpolation from September to December 2019 and January to December 2020, as shown in Figures 4 and 5.

The points of occurrence in the southern region of the study area are related to one another, but their similarity is inversely related to that of the study area's northern region. This inverse similarity is owing to the fact that there were no case in the northern region of the study area. Between September and December 2019, there was no single incident in the Zaki,

Gamawa, Gadau, Jama'are, Katagum, Danban, Shira, Giade, Misau, and Darazo local government areas all located in the northern portion of the research area. It's possible that the vector hadn't visited this location at the

time, or there aren't enough favourable elements, such as woodland, stagnant water, and climatic factors, to support the *larvae's* life and illness transmission.

Figure 4: Distribution of yellow fever in Bauchi from September-December 2019
Source: Field Survey (2022)

It's also possible that the drainage systems in the built-up areas are constantly clean. It's also likely that residents in the area have faithfully follow the instructions for using insecticide-treated nets. As illustrated in Figure 5, some areas in the Ningi, Jama'are, Warji, Toro, Ganjuwa, and Tafawa Balewa local government areas experienced between zero and one yellow fever occurrences/cases in 2020.

Similarly, between ten and eleven cases were reported in several counties and/or locations in Ganjuwa local government. Reasons for these incidents may not be unconnected with the presence of a dam and forested areas in the region. Ganjuwa is also close to the epicenter of the yellow fever outbreak (Yankari game reserve in Alkaleri Local Government Area of Bauchi State); this thus makes it simple for the yellow fever virus's vector (*Aedes aegypti*) to migrate and infiltrate.

Figure 5: Distribution of yellow in Bauchi from January-December 2020
 Source: Field Survey (2022)

Because these maps are simple to comprehend, they can help raise awareness of this disease (Yellow fever) among the residents of the study region, encouraging them to engage in best practices that will restrict the spread and/or eliminate the disease completely.

THE PATTERN OF SPREAD IN THE YELLOW FEVER OUTBREAK

The distribution patterns of yellow fever cases in 2019 and 2020 were examined in relation to the outbreak's attribute values in the study area (Gri, 2019). The propagation of the yellow fever outbreak in Bauchi state in 2019 followed a random pattern. As indicated in Table 2, the Moran's Index is negative (-0.070041), indicating that neighboring locations have dissimilar modes of yellow fever case dissemination at $P = 0.775496$.

Table 2: Global Moran's I Summary of 2019 yellow fever cases in Bauchi state, Nigeria

Parameters	Values
Moran's Index:	-0.070041
Expected Index:	-0.008929
Variance:	0.045918
z-score:	-0.285194
p-value:	0.775496

Source: Author's Findings (2022)

The case of yellow fever outbreak in 2020 was completely random. Table 3 shows that Moran's I value (0.074746) and Z-score (0.556891) were both positive at the 0.577602 significant level.

Table 3: Global Moran's I Summary of 2020 yellow fever cases in Bauchi state, Nigeria

Parameters	Values
Moran's Index:	0.074746
Expected Index:	-0.028571
Variance:	0.034420
z-score:	0.556891
p-value:	0.577602

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Because the Z-score is smaller than 2.58, there is a greater than 1% possibility that the pattern of yellow fever spread in 2020 within the study is due to random chance, implying that similar variables were responsible for the spread of yellow fever across the research area's neighborhoods.

YELLOW FEVER HOTSPOTS IN BAUCHI STATE

Because of the favorable benefits of vaccination initiatives, the yellow fever virus was previously thought to be on the decline. However, the recent global spread of yellow

fever virus has demonstrated the virus's ongoing threat to human populations, as well as the need for ongoing vaccination campaigns and vigilant surveillance of occasional outbreaks in rural areas. Using spatial optimal hotspot analysis, the scope of the yellow fever outbreak cases was assessed in relation to county location. With a graded symbol, the locations with high, moderate, and low outbreak cases were emphasized. As illustrated in Figure 6, Alkaleri and a portion of the Bauchi local government area bordering Alkaleri North experienced a high number of yellow fever infections in 2019.

Figure 6: Optimised Hotspot of Yellow Fever Cases in Bauchi state in 2019

Source: Field Survey (2022)

This high occurrence could be attributable to the fact that the outbreak began in the Yankari game reserve, which is part of Alkaleri. The location of Yankari game reserve may be held accountable for the outbreak because it provides a suitable ecological environment for the yellow fever virus's vector (*Aedes aegypti*). Many stagnant water, streams and tributaries alongside dense woodland where mosquitos breeds can be found in this area. The presence of monkeys in the Yankari game reserve could also have aided the disease's spread in the region, as this non-human primate was discovered to be a major determinant of yellow fever transmission in a similar study conducted by de Thoisy *et al.*, (2020).

Monkeys are reservoirs of yellow fever virus that could get into an area with naive populations and contribute viral dissemination. This could also be one of the reasons for the high number of yellow fever cases in southern Bauchi, as a large population of monkeys from the Yankari game reserve travels long distances to other areas of the region. According to the spatial optimized hotspot analysis, the yellow fever epidemic cases in Bauchi in 2020 were concentrated in Ganjuwa local government area of Bauchi state. Yellow fever cases were high in Ganjuwa local government area of the state at 99 percent and 95 percent confidence levels, implying that Ganjuwa county was the hotspot of yellow fever cases in 2020, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Optimised Hotspot of Yellow Fever Cases in Bauchi state in 2020
Source: Field Survey (2022)

The high number of yellow fever cases in Ganjuwa in 2020 could be attributed to the presence of the Gubi dam, which could serve as a breeding ground for the yellow fever virus vector (*Aedes aegypti*). This is because, water outflows from the dam usually spreads across the area, causing stagnant water during the rainy season. Sumu Wildlife Park in Ganjuwa may also favor *Aedes aegypti* hatching due to stagnant water and shrubs necessary for the park's wildlife's existence. In Ganjuwa, human activities such as farming and mining can encourage mosquito breeding. The mosquitoes' life cycle is aided by drainage systems that retain waste water. Studies have shown that *Aedes aegypti* expected life span can be attained at high temperatures of between 16.5 and 35 degrees Celsius (Hamrick *et al.*, 2017). According to regional geographic statistics, Bauchi state average temperature for the previous ten years was 35.5°C. This average temperature encourages the life cycle of the

mosquito which leads to their high number and consequently an increase in viral circulation. Except for Bauchi South, there were no major cases in other local government areas of Bauchi state in 2019. In 2020, the outbreak had a cold spot in Ganjuwa's northwestern region, while cases in Warji, Ningi, Tafawa Balewa, and Bauchi local government areas were not grouped, making the hotspot statistically unimportant.

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS INFLUENCING DISTRIBUTION OF YELLOW FEVER IN BAUCHI STATE

Figure 8 shows the results of land use and land cover analysis of landsat8 satellite images between September 2019 and December 2020. In the research area, agricultural activity occupies a bigger share of the land surface (83.79 percent). 3.50 percent of the study's surface is covered by water, 1.21 percent by built-up areas, and 11.50 percent by forest. In

comparison to the northern section of the state, the southern part of the state had higher vegetative cover. This is because the southern

region has more water sources and rivers, although the northern region receives more annual rainfall than the southern region (Eludoyin *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 8: Land use and land cover of Bauchi state
Source: Field Survey (2022)

The northern part is more developed than the southern; that is to say, urbanisation is rapidly expanding in the region due to the flat terrain and lack of greenery.

Using Multicriteria analysis, areas vulnerable to yellow fever were assessed based on environmental and climatic characteristics that promote yellow fever transmission and spread. On the basis of each risk factor, the locations in Bauchi State that were most vulnerable, moderately vulnerable, and less vulnerable to yellow fever were identified, as illustrated in Figure 9. Because transmitting mosquitoes can be found at various altitudes, altitude is thus not a factor of high consideration, although at over 2.3km, the mosquito will be unable to fly far (De Paiva *et al.*, 2019). Temperature gradients

caused by altitude, on the other hand, have an impact on mosquito and virus survivability. Because the altitude in Bauchi state is less than 2.3 kilometers, the research area, particularly in the south-western part, is extremely vulnerable to yellow fever because the altitude encourages vector flight. Built-up and the presence of mosquitoes were given lesser weights to minimize overlapping of importance.

Built-up areas will always have drainages with stagnant water where the vector's larvae will develop; however, this has made the northern part of the study area highly susceptible to yellow fever. The built-up area in the southern portion of the study area are highly sensitive to yellow fever because of their close proximity to the forested region of the study area.

Figure 9: Yellow fever risk factors in the Study Area

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The existence of non-human primates (monkeys) and forests were assumed to be decisive variables in the prevalence of yellow fever even if the location of mosquitoes transmitting yellow fever are Restricted to a particular geographical location. Although the *Aedes aegypti* inhabit the woods; hence it is assumed that the forest aspect better depicts the distribution of *Aedes aegypti* as transmitters of yellow fever. Major local governments of the study area are extremely susceptible to yellow fever when monkeys, mosquitoes and forest are considered as risk factors. These three criteria are partially related in that the monkeys and mosquitoes inhabit the forest. The entire research region is particularly vulnerable to these three elements as these are the key determinant of the yellow fever spread. The virus is spread by monkeys, who wander from the forest to urban areas in search of food, and some are kept as pets.

This poses a major risk of yellow fever spreading in the study area, which explains

why monkeys are such a high risk factor for yellow fever in the study area. The vector, *Aedes aegypti*, may fly for roughly 45 kilometers at a time, rest, and then resume their journey. This is one of the characteristics that makes them a critical risk factor, implying that the research region is susceptible to yellow fever. The northern section of the study area is at high danger of yellow fever spread, hence temperature was used as a determining factor. The significant susceptibility demonstrated by temperature in the northern county of this research area is due to high temperatures that promote mosquito larva formation. In a similar study conducted in Brazil by Vasconcelos *et al.*, (2001), it was discovered that as the temperature rises, the virus spreads faster.

Each risk factor connected to the prevalence of yellow fever in people was assigned importance based on the factors analyzed in Figure 2, and then integrated using weighted sum overlay to indicate locations prone to the spread of yellow fever, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Yellow Fever Vulnerable Areas in Bauchi State
Source: Field Survey (2022)

Alkaleri, Ganjuwa, Darazo, Toro, Ningi, Giade, and parts of Bauchi local government that bordered Ganjuwa local government are among the counties in the research area that are extremely sensitive to yellow fever. The whole state of Bauchi is fairly sensitive to yellow fever, with the exception of parts of the Zaki, Gamawa, and Gadau local governments, which have demonstrated a low risk of an epidemic. The differences in the yellow fever vulnerability map were due to a higher priority being placed on factors that directly influence the presence of vectors, such as forest type and

distance, as well as the presence of non-human primates susceptible to the virus and the presence of transmitting mosquitoes. As a result of these conditions, several areas of Bauchi state have been linked to a high risk of yellow fever.

The region of Bauchi state that had significant occurrences of yellow fever in 2019 and 2020 matched with some of the counties designated as extremely sensitive, according to the overlay of incidences on the vulnerability map (Figures 11 and 12).

Figure 11: Yellow fever vulnerable areas showing 2019 cases in Bauchi state

Source: Field Survey (2022).

As illustrated in Figure 13, both the 2019 and 2020 yellow fever case maps were combined and superimposed on the vulnerability map, and the points of incidence with a large number

of cases also matched with the counties that had been identified as extremely vulnerable in the Multicriteria analysis.

Figure 12: Yellow fever vulnerable areas showing 2020 in Bauchi state

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 12: Yellow fever vulnerable areas in year 2019 and 2020 in Bauchi State

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The correlation between the points of occurrence of yellow fever outbreaks in 2019 and 2020 and the points of vulnerability could be attributable to the presence of conservation units such as waterbodies, forests, and agriculture, all of which provide ideal habitat for the vector. *Aedes aegypti* infestation may occur in high-vulnerability locations surrounding the Bauchi metropolitan zone, increasing the risk of Yellow Fever cases. Because the most vulnerable locations revealed in the Multicriteria analysis aligned with the places where yellow fever was detected in 2019 and 2020, the factors, weights, and amounts were consistent and accurate.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Bauchi state is threatened by the spread of yellow fever outbreaks with more widespread in the southern portion of the state. Alkaleri and Ganjuwa local government areas are regarded

as the hotspots of yellow fever according to the 2019 and 2020 cases recorded. Physical and environmental factors plays significant role in distribution and spread of the disease within the study area. Based on these findings, the following recommendations are provided.

- i. National primary health care research and development agency and other healthcare stakeholders should ensure that yellow fever vaccine are administered, not only to the entire population of the study area but also to non-human primate carrier host of the virus such as monkey since they are kept as pet
- ii. The Ministry of Health should provide insecticidal treated nets to residents of the study area as mitigation measures for vector control and/or aerial carry out fumigation of the environment to keep the vector larvae at bay.

iii. National primary health care research and development agency and other healthcare stakeholders in Bauchi state should consistently perform surveillance in order

to avert future re-emerging of the yellow fever outbreak in the region

iv. Future investigations should be carried out to measure more precisely the temperature threshold for Yellow Fever in human instances.

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